

Comparison of Zoom Webinars and Live Events on Microsoft Teams Webinar Platform for E-Learning Delivery

Inderpal Virdee

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to compare the licenced versions of Zoom Webinars and Live Events on Microsoft Teams for live webinars and pre-recorded e-learning and training. As no comprehensive comparison of main the features for exists, this was conducted. It is hoped that this research will prove useful to other organisations exploring and evaluating e-learning and training technologies for their organisation.

Webinar Platforms

Two webinar platforms that were investigated. These were:

1. Zoom Webinars – Version: 5.05
2. Live Events on Microsoft Teams – Version: 4.4.41.0

It should be noted that all the feature and functions of platforms change over time.

Method

Full licences were obtained for Zoom Webinars (including Zoom Pro licences) and Live Events on Microsoft Teams for this assessment.

Specification of technologies used to assess both webinar platforms:

- Devices included laptops, tablets and smartphones.
- Operating systems used were Windows, Apple and Android.
- Internet browsers used were Chrome, Firefox, IE, Safari and Samsung Internet.
- Smartphone and tablet apps used were Zoom and Microsoft Teams.
- Internet connection methods used were Wifi and Ethernet connection.

Assessment Details

- Four members were used to carry out the test.
- Assessments were carried out 100% remotely.
- Systematic tests were carried from April to June 2020.

Comparison between Zoom Webinars and Live Events

OVERALL SUMMARY	
Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
User	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The host, co-producer and presenters all require licences to have the full controls and features. Having a Zoom Webinar licence allows up to 100 panellists to interact during the webinar. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The presenters all require licences to have the full controls and features. Allows up to 10,000 attendees to watch passively.
Webinar Setup	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a lot of control over the registration setup process overall. Basic and advance automatic email responders with personalised branding. The ability to Live Streaming across platforms. The ability to set up Polls before and during the webinar. The Panellists/Attendees can upvote and comment on other Panellists/Attendees Q&A. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic registration setup. No automatic email responders No personalised branding. The ability to Live Streaming is customisable. No ability to set up polls. Attendees can participate in a controlled Q&A.
Connection Setup	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Able to connect via telephone or another digital device. Able to connect via browser or app. The host, producers and co-hosts should use a hard-line/Ethernet wire when running a webinar. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Able to connect via telephone or another digital device. Able to connect via browser or app. The host, producers and co-hosts should use a hard-line/Ethernet wire when running a webinar.
Login Setup	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is possible for a panellist or an attendee to login using the same account from 2 different devices. There is an option to force the user to login using 1 device only. Anonymous users cannot view the webinar without registering a Zoom account. Furthermore, it is possible to bar anonymous users by having a list of Panellists/Attendees that are required to register and be approved by the host before the start of the webinar. The alternative login should be deactivated to increase security. There is a Two-Factor Authentication Sign in. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is possible for a panellist or an attendee to login using the same account from 2 different devices whether it is a public or private link.

Security Setup	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Great control over password security. • Controllable user IP Address Access. • No end-to-end encryption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No enhanced password security. • No controllable user IP Address Access. • Provides End-to-end encryption.
Before Starting	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Panellists/Attendees can join from multiple devices. • No Waiting Room for panellists/attendees. • Additional Producers and Presenters can be added. • Has a recording disclaimer notice. Asks panellists/attendees for consent when a recording starts. Asks the host to confirm before starting a recording. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Panellists/Attendees can join from multiple devices. • No Waiting Room for panellists/attendees. • Additional Producers and Presenters can be added. • No recording disclaimer notice. No consent asked from panellists/attendees when a recording starts. No confirmation asked by the host before a recording starts.
People Management	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The webinar can be locked to prevent registered and anonymous users from joining. • The Host can promote an Attendee to become a Panellist or a Host. • A visible attendee list. • Attendees can be removed from the webinar at any time. • Host, Producers and Presenters can chat privately between each other. • Breakout Rooms can be used for activities and discussion in small groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No locked webinar. Allowing any users to join the webinar. • No promotion of Attendee's to Panellist's or Host's. • No visible attendee list. • Attendees can be removed from the webinar at any time but not anonymous viewers. • Host, Producers and Presenters can chat privately between each other. • No Breakout Rooms for activities and discussion in small groups.
Video Management	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice Session available before recording live. • Able to pause, stop and re-record countless times. • A recording can be stored in the cloud or on the host's local drive directly. • Live captions can be written by a person or using and API. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice Session available before recording live. • Not able to pause, stop and re-record. Once a recording is stopped the whole event ends and cannot be re-recorded. • A recording is only stored in the cloud. It can be downloaded onto a local drive after the event. • No live captions
Sharing Management	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Host, Presenters and Panellists/Attendees can all share screens. • Remote screen control can only be used if there are no Breakout Rooms. If the Breakout Rooms are used then there is no Remote screen control access. • The Host can control the Presenters, Panellists and Attendees microphones. • The Presenters and attendees can use a whiteboard. • Screen drawing tools are available to everyone with the ability to download the scribbles and save the files separately. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only the Host can share the screens. • No Remote screen controls. • No microphones ability for Attendees. • No whiteboard. • No Screen drawing tools. • No files can be exchanged through the chat.

Presentation Management	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any file can be shared on screen. • Embedded PowerPoint Videos can be seen and heard. Use the “Share computer sound” setting to include sound. • Streaming internet videos from websites can be seen and heard. Use the “Share computer sound” setting to include sound. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any file can be shared on screen. • Embedded PowerPoint Videos can be seen and heard. Use the “Include system audio” setting to include sound. • Streaming internet videos from websites can be seen and heard. Use the “Include system audio” setting to include sound.
After a Webinar	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post Webinar Survey can be used to link to an external survey. • Recorded video and audio files can be downloaded and edited. • Available reporting files for download: Registration Report, Panellists/Attendees List, Chat History, Q&A List, Performance Report and Poll Report. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No Post Webinar Survey link. • Recorded video and audio files can be downloaded and edited. • Available reporting files for download: Panellists/Attendees List, Chat History and Q&A List.

Details of Zoom Webinars and Live Events on Microsoft Teams Features

User Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- The host, co-producer and presenters all require licences to have the full controls and features.
- Having a Zoom Webinar licence allows up to 100 panellists to interact during the webinar.

Live Events:

- The presenters all require licences to have the full controls and features.
- Allows up to 10,000 passive attendees.

USERS		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Host		
> Producer	Required	Required
> Co-Producer(s)	Yes (licenced user needed)	Yes
> Presenter(s)	Yes	Yes
Panellist		
> Maximum number Panellists	100 (Webinar licence)	N/A
> Panellist's ability during the webinar	Interactive	Passive (Q&A)
Attendee		
Maximum Attendees	100	10,000
> Internal (ISI only)	Yes	Yes
> External (Invited Public)	Yes	Yes
> External (Anonymous)	Yes	Yes
> Attendees ability during the webinar	Passive (Q&A)	Passive (Q&A)

Webinar Setup Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- There is a lot of control over the registration setup process overall.
- Basic and advance automatic email responders with personalised branding.
- The ability to Live Streaming across platforms.
- The ability to set up Polls before and during the webinar.
- The Panellists/Attendees can upvote and comment on other Panellists/Attendees Q&A.

Live Events:

- Basic registration setup.
- No automatic email responders
- No personalised branding.
- The ability to Live Streaming is customisable.
- No ability to set up polls.
- Attendees can participate in a controlled Q&A.

WEBINAR SETUP		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Registration Setup		
> Only authenticated users on Zoom or MS Teams can join	Yes	Yes
> Required Registration	Yes	No
> Automatically Approve	Yes	Yes
> Manually Approve	Yes	No
> Notification of registration	Yes	No
> Registration fee	Yes (PayPal)	No
Registration options		
> Close registration after event date	Yes	No
> Restrict number of registrants	Yes	(internal attendees only)
> Allow panellists/attendees to join from multiple devices	Yes	Yes
> Show social share buttons on registration page	Yes	No
Tracking Pixel		
> Keep track of how many users visit your website or see your advertisement	Yes	No
Branding		
> Logo	Yes	No
> Banner	Yes	No
> Webinar registration page themes	Yes	No
Email Responders		
> Basic auto email responder	Yes	No
> Advance auto email responder	Yes	No
Live Streaming Across Platforms		
> Facebook	Yes	No
> YouTube	Yes	No

> Custom	Yes	Yes
> Into the Absorb LMS	No	No
Polls		
> Setup before the webinar	Yes	No
> During before the webinar	Yes	No
> Poll questions - Single Choice	Yes	No
> Poll questions - Multiple Choice	Yes	No
> Anonymous responses	Yes	No
> Polls window shows results during a webinar	No	No
> Create polls in real-time	Yes	No
Q&A		
> Allow anonymous questions	Yes	Yes
> Panellists/Attendees can view all Q&A	Yes	No
> Panellists/Attendees can view selected Q&A by the Host	Yes	Yes
> Panellists/Attendees can upvote	Yes	No
> Panellists/Attendees can comment	Yes	No
Producers can publish or dismiss questions	Yes	Yes

Connection Setup Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- Able to connect via telephone or another digital device.
- Able to connect via browser or app.
- The host, producers and co-hosts should use a hard-line/Ethernet wire when running a webinar.

Live Events:

- Able to connect via telephone or another digital device.
- Able to connect via browser or app.
- The host, producers and co-hosts should use a hard-line/Ethernet wire when running a webinar.

CONNECTION SETUP		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Connection		
Connect from a Telephone	Yes	Yes
Connect from any Device	Yes	Yes
Connect from any Browser	Yes	Yes
Connect from Zoom or MS Teams app	Yes	Yes
Hard-line/Ethernet Wire recommended by platform	Yes	Yes
WiFi recommended by platform	No	No

Login Setup Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- It is possible for a panellist or an attendee to login using the same account from 2 different devices. There is an option to force the user to login using 1 device only.
- Anonymous users cannot view the webinar without registering a Zoom account. Furthermore, it is possible to bar anonymous users by having a list of Panellists/Attendees that are required to register and be approved by the host before the start of the webinar.
- The alternative login should be deactivated to increase security.
- There is a Two-Factor Authentication Sign in.

Live Events:

- It is possible for a panellist or an attendee to login using the same account from 2 different devices whether it is a public or private link.

LOGIN SETUP		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Login		
> Logging in using the same account on 2 different devices	Yes	Yes
>> Anonymous (browser)	No	Yes
>> Attendee	Optional	Yes
>> Panellist	Optional	No
>> Host	Optional	No
> Can an anonymous person view the live webinar without registering?	No	Yes
Alternative Login		
Alternative Users Sign-in	Optional	No
> Users sign in with Google	Optional	No
> Users sign in with Facebook	Optional	No
> Sign in with Two-Factor Authentication	Yes	No

Security Setup Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- Great control over password security.
- Controllable user IP Address Access.
- No end-to-end encryption

Live Events:

- No enhanced password security.
- No controllable user IP Address Access.
- Provides End-to-end encryption.

SECURITY SETUP		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Password		
> Enhanced Password Requirement	Yes	No
>> Have a minimum password length	Yes	No
>> Have at least 1 special character	Yes	No
>> Cannot contain consecutive characters	Yes	No
>> Use enhanced weak password detection	Yes	No
> Password Policy	Yes	No
>> New users need to change their passwords upon first sign-in	Yes	No
>> Password expires automatically	Yes	No
>> Users cannot reuse any password used in the previous number of times	Yes	No
>> Users can change their password a maximum number of times every 24 hours	Yes	No
IP Address		
> IP Address Access Control	Yes	No
Encryption		
> End-to-end encryption with 256-bit Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)	No	Yes

Before Starting Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- Panellists/Attendees can join from multiple devices.
- No Waiting Room for panellists/attendees.
- Additional Producers and Presenters can be added.
- Has a recording disclaimer notice. Asks panellists/attendees for consent when a recording starts. Asks the host to confirm before starting a recording.

Live Events:

- Panellists/Attendees can join from multiple devices.
- No Waiting Room for panellists/attendees.
- Additional Producers and Presenters can be added.
- No recording disclaimer notice. No consent asked from panellists/attendees when a recording starts. No confirmation asked by the host before a recording starts.

BEFORE STARTING A WEBINAR		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Before Broadcasting Live		
> Allow panellists/attendees to join from multiple devices	Yes	Yes
Waiting Room		
> A room for Panellists/Attendees to go into before a webinar starts	No	No
Production Team		
> Add more Producers	Yes	Yes
> Add more Presenters	Yes	Yes
Before Recording		
> Recording disclaimer notice to participants before recording	Yes	No
> Ask panellists/attendees for consent when a recording starts	Yes	No
> Ask host to confirm before starting a recording	Yes	No

People Management Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- The webinar can be locked to prevent registered and anonymous users from joining.
- The Host can promote an Attendee to become a Panellist or a Host.
- A visible attendee list.
- Attendees can be removed from the webinar at any time.
- Host, Producers and Presenters can chat privately between each other.
- Breakout Rooms can be used for activities and discussion in small groups.

Live Events:

- No locked webinar. Allowing any users to join the webinar.
- No promotion of Attendee's to Panellist's or Host's.
- No visible attendee list.
- Attendees can be removed from the webinar at any time but not anonymous viewers.
- Host, Producers and Presenters can chat privately between each other.
- No Breakout Rooms for activities and discussion in small groups.

PEOPLE MANAGEMENT DURING A WEBINAR		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Webinar Room		
> Lock the webinar so no one joins	Yes	No
Manage Participants Roles		
> Make Panellists into Hosts	Yes	No
> Make Attendee's into Panellists	Yes	No
> Attendee's List during the webinar	Yes	No
Remove Attendees		
> Attendees	Yes	Yes
> Anonymous	N/A	No (Public Webinar)
Private Chat During the Webinar		
Host, Producers and Presenters	Yes	Yes
Registered panellists/attendees can chat to each other (from single device)	No	No
Anonymous attendees can chat to each other (browser)	No	No
Breakout Rooms		
Rooms for panellists/attendees to do activities in	Yes	No

Video Management Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- Practice Session available before recording live.
- Able to pause, stop and re-record countless times.
- A recording be stored in the cloud or on the host's local drive directly.
- Live captions can be written by a person or using and API.

Live Events:

- Practice Session available before recording live.
- Not able to pause, stop and re-record. Once a recording is stopped the whole event ends and cannot be re-recorded.
- A recording is only stored in the cloud. It can be downloaded onto a local drive after the event.
- No live captions

VIDEO MANAGEMENT DURING A WEBINAR		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Recording while Live		
Enable Practice Session before recording	Yes	Yes
Pause, Stop, Re-record	Yes	No
Recording Storage		
Record the webinar on local drive	Yes	No
Record the webinar in the cloud	Yes	Yes
Editable video recording	Yes	Yes
Editable audio recording	Yes	Yes
Live Captions		
Host types captions	Yes	No
Assign person types captions	Yes	No
API integration	Yes	No

Sharing Management Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- The Host, Presenters and Panellists/Attendees can all share screens.
- Remote screen control can only be used if there are no Breakout Rooms. If the Breakout Rooms are used then there is no Remote screen control access.
- The Host can control the Presenters, Panellists and Attendees microphones.
- The Presenters and attendees can use a whiteboard.
- Screen drawing tools are available to everyone with the ability to download the scribbles and save the files separately.
- No files can be exchanged through the chat.

Live Events:

- Only the Host can share the screens.
- No Remote screen controls.
- No microphones ability for Attendees.
- No whiteboard.
- No Screen drawing tools.
- No files can be exchanged through the chat.

SHARING MANAGEMENT DURING A WEBINAR		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Screen Sharing		
Host can share screens	Yes	Yes
Presenters can share screens	Yes	No
Panellists/Attendees can share screens	Yes	No
HD video for screen sharing	Yes	No
Remote Control		
Remote screen control	Yes (but you lose the Breakout Room function)	No
Audio Sharing		
Host controls panellist's mic	Yes	Yes
Host controls participant/attendee's mic	Yes	Not available
Whiteboard		
Presenters and attendees can use a whiteboard	Yes	No
Screen Drawing Tool		
Draw on any screen	Yes	No
Write on any screen	Yes	No
Download image of any screen	Yes	No
Files		
Able to share files during a webinar	No	No

Presentation Management Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- Any file can be shared on screen.
- Embedded PowerPoint Videos can be seen and heard. Use the “Share computer sound” setting to include sound.
- Streaming internet videos from websites can be seen and heard. Use the “Share computer sound” setting to include sound.

Live Events:

- Any file can be shared on screen.
- Embedded PowerPoint Videos can be seen and heard. Use the “Include system audio” setting to include sound.
- Streaming internet videos from websites can be seen and heard. Use the “Include system audio” setting to include sound.

PRESENTATION MANAGEMENT A DURING WEBINAR		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Files		
Any file can be shared on screen	Yes	Yes
PowerPoint (PPT)		
> Presenter’s PPT can be queued easily	Yes	Yes
Embedded PowerPoint Videos		
> Videos can be seen	Yes	Yes
> Videos play sound	Yes (Share computer sound)	Yes (Include system audio)
Streaming Internet Videos		
> Videos can be seen	Yes	Yes
> Videos play sound	Yes (Share computer sound)	Yes (Include system audio)

After a Webinar Summary

Zoom Webinar:

- Post Webinar Survey can be used to link to an external survey.
- Recorded video and audio files can be downloaded and edited.
- Available reporting files for download: Registration Report, Panellists/Attendees List, Chat History, Q&A List, Performance Report and Poll Report.

Live Events:

- No Post Webinar Survey link.
- Recorded video and audio files can be downloaded and edited.
- Available reporting files for download: Panellists/Attendees List, Chat History and Q&A List.

AFTER A WEBINAR		
Item	Zoom Webinar Licenced version	Microsoft Live Events Licenced version
Post Webinar		
> Post attendee URL	Yes	No
> Post Webinar Survey	Yes (external survey)	No
> Social Media Share Description	Yes	No
Recordings		
Editable video recording	Yes	Yes
Audio recording only	Yes	No
Editable audio recording	Yes	Yes
Reporting/History Files		
Registration Report	Yes	No
Panellists/Attendees List	Yes	Yes
Chat History	Yes	Yes
Q&A List	Yes	Yes
Performance Report	Yes	No (Only in real-time)
Poll Report	Yes	No

References

Microsoft (2020). Collaborative Microsoft products. www.microsoft.com

Zoom (2020). Video conferencing technology. Link: <https://zoom.us>